

NuPhys 2026: Prospects in Neutrino Physics

Liquid Detector Technologies For Neutrino Physics

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Outline

- Why liquid-based detectors?
- Water Cherenkov Detectors
 - Hyper-Kamiokande
- Liquid Argon Time Projection Chambers
 - DUNE
- Liquid Scintillator Detectors
 - JUNO
- Opaque Media – LiquidO
- Conclusions

Why Liquid Detectors?

Key challenge: extremely weak interaction of neutrinos with matter

- **Large target mass** (typically kiloton to megaton scale)
- **Low background environment**
 - Underground operation to suppress cosmic rays
 - Radiopure detector materials and shielding
- **Efficient particle detection**
 - Sensitivity to charged leptons and hadrons. Low energy thresholds for solar and SN
- **Good energy reconstruction** (Crucial for oscillation measurements and mass ordering)
- **Event topology reconstruction**
 - Flavor identification. Separation of signal and background
- **Precise timing capabilities**
- **Scalability and long-term stability**

Different liquid detector technologies represent different optimizations of these requirements

Liquid Detector Landscape

Water Cherenkov Detectors

Liquid Argon TPC Detectors

Liquid Scintillator Detectors

+ Opaque Detectors (emerging technology)

Water Cherenkov Detectors

Produces coherent light at a characteristic angle: $\cos \theta = \frac{1}{\beta n}$

Ring pattern encodes:

- Particle type (e-like vs μ -like)
- Direction
- Energy (via light yield)

Why water?

- Cheap and available in large volumes
- Long optical attenuation length
- Well-understood optical properties

Strengths:

- Very large detector volumes (hundreds of ktons)
- Excellent direction reconstruction
- Proven technology

Limitations:

- High Cherenkov threshold
- Limited hadronic energy reconstruction
- Limited event-by-event particle identification at low energies

Hyper-Kamiokande

- **Next-generation water Cherenkov detector in Japan**
- Fiducial mass FD: ~ 190 kton ($\times 8.4$ Super-Kamiokande), total 260 kton
- Located ~ 295 km from J-PARC neutrino beam, upgraded 1.3 MW ($\times 2.5$ higher power)

$\sim 2028 - \dots$

Photodetection system:

$\sim 20,000$ 50cm high-QE PMTs

- Improved photon detection efficiency
- Better charge and timing resolution
- Pressure resistance (1.25 MPa)

~ 800 mPMT modules integrated as a hybrid configuration (Improving Cherenkov ring reconstruction in detector corners)

20% photocoverage

1996 - ...

More info: [Robert Kralik's talk](#)

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Performance highlights:

- Excellent angular resolution
- Good electron/muon separation
- High statistics due to large mass

Physics goals:

- CP violation in the lepton sector
- Neutrino mass ordering (atmospheric neutrino data)
- Proton decay searches
- Solar and supernova neutrinos

$\sim 2028 - \dots$

Liquid Argon Time Projection Chambers

Why LArTPC?

- Neutrino interaction in liquid argon produces ionization + scintillation light
- Ionization electrons drift under an electric field
- Drifted electrons are collected on segmented anode planes
- 3D reconstruction from charge readout + drift time
- Scintillation VUV light (~ 128 nm) used for event timing, triggering and complementary calorimetry

Strengths:

- mm-scale spatial resolution
- Excellent particle identification
- Detailed hadronic reconstruction

Challenges:

- Cryogenic operation (87 K).
- Ultra-high argon purity requirements.
- Cost and scalability

DUNE

- DUNE is a **next-generation long-baseline neutrino experiment** based in (USA).
- The Far Detector will consist of **four LArTPC modules** located 1300 km from the neutrino source at Fermilab.
- Each module **10 kt** (fiducial) **of liquid argon** and combines fine-grained 3D event imaging with calorimetric reconstruction and scintillation light detection.

Physics goals:

- Neutrino mass ordering
- CP violation in the lepton sector
- Octant of θ_{23}
- Non-beam physics (atmospherics, solar...)
- SN neutrino burst
- Proton decay searches

DUNE FD modules

More info: [Patricia Sanchez's talk](#)

- **FD horizontal drift:** ionization electrons drift horizontally toward anode plane assemblies (APAs) located on the sides.
- A central cathode plane divides the detector volume into two independent drift regions, with maximum drift distances of ~ 3.6 m.
- Charge is collected on wire planes, while scintillation light is detected by photon detection systems integrated within the APAs.

- **FD vertical drift:** ionization electrons drift vertically toward charge readout planes located at the top and bottom.
- A horizontal cathode plane placed at mid-height divides the detector into two vertical drift regions.
- Longer drift distances and potentially reduced readout complexity, at the cost of higher voltages and more stringent purity requirements.

Liquid Scintillator Detectors

TRANSPARENT

Why liquid scintillators?

- Combination of solvent + fluor (ex: LAB+PPO)
- Charged particles excite scintillator molecules
- Isotropic emission of scintillation light
- High light yield ($\sim 10,000$ photons/MeV)
- Long attenuation lengths (with purification)
- Light yield proportional to deposited energy

Strengths:

- Very low energy thresholds (sub-MeV)
- Excellent energy resolution
- Precision calorimetry
- High stability
- Ideal for reactor, solar, and geo-neutrinos

Limitations:

- Weak topology reconstruction
- Directionality largely lost
- Particle ID relies on timing and pulse shape discrimination

- Next-generation large liquid scintillator detector - **20 kton liquid scintillator** (China)
- ~35 m diameter acrylic sphere
- Surrounded by water Cherenkov detector

Innovations:

- **Total light level >1200 p.e. / MeV**
- high transparency and high radiopurity
- Dual PMT system for dynamic range
- ~ 18,000 20-inch PMTs + ~ 25,000 3-inch PMTs
- Photocathode coverage 78%
- PMT QE ~30%
- **Unprecedented energy resolution** $\sim 3\%/\sqrt{(E/\text{MeV})}$
- Optical calibration systems E_{scale} uncert. < 1%

Key limitation:

Limited event topology reconstruction

More info: [Davide Basilico's talk](#)

Physics program:

- Neutrino mass ordering via reactor neutrinos
- Precision oscillation parameters
- Solar neutrinos
- Geo-neutrinos
- Supernova neutrinos

LiquidO: novel detection approach

Transparent: Today's technology
Topology information washed out

Usual Transparent
Liquid Scintillator
Detectors

Reactor $\bar{\nu}_e \rightarrow e^+$ tagging

- ★ Hard to distinguish from an e^- or γ interaction
- ★ Topological Particle Identification (PID) is a challenge in MeV neutrino detection

LiquidO: novel detection approach

Transparent: Today's technology
Topology information washed out

Opaque: LiquidO technology
Light clustering

LiquidO: novel detection approach

Unprecedented imaging capabilities

- ★ **Discrimination** of individual **e⁺**, **e⁻** and **γ** events @MeV
- ★ Matter/Antimatter separation
- ★ **Powerful Background Rejection**
- ★ A self-segmented detector (no need of dead material)

- ★ e-/ γ discrimination of 1000/1 possible

Example: Detect antineutrinos through IBD

LiquidO detection technique

1) Opaque scintillator

- ★ Originally using **NoWaSH (NW)** (New opaque Wax Scintillator, Heidelberg)
- ★ Linear Alkyl Benzene (~80 wt.%) + PPO (~0.3 wt.%) + Paraffin Wax (~20 wt.%)
[arXiv:1908.03334](https://arxiv.org/abs/1908.03334)

- ★ **LiquidO R&D extensive field:** reduction of the paraffin concentration, new μ Crystal scintillators [arXiv:1807.00628](https://arxiv.org/abs/1807.00628), water-based opaque scintillator [arXiv:2406.13054](https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.13054), emulsion...

- 2) Maximal light collection by a **dense array of wavelength-shifting (WLS) fibers**
- 3) **Fast time resolution (electronics + SiPMs)** (< 1 ns)

Excellent vertex resolution (mm scale)

Mini-LiquidO prototype

[arXiv: 2503.02541](https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.02541)

- ★ 10 L detector
- ★ 56 WLS fibres (Kuraray B3), 15 mm pitch
- ★ Single readout with SiPMs (Hamamatsu S13360-1350PE)
- ★ e- from monoenergetic beam (^{90}Sr -Y) [0.4-1.8 MeV]
- ★ T cycle [5,40] $^{\circ}\text{C}$ — transparent vs opaque
- ★ Very fast electronics: fast low-power custom preamplifier with sub-ns rise time
- ★ 64-channel WaveCatcher system for waveform digitization (ps time res.)

Goal: Stochastic light confinement observation

Mini-LiquidO prototype

Light confinement demonstration

Transparent simulation

Opaque simulation

- ★ Absolute response analysis (data-driven) — G4-simulation scaling
- ★ Expected response LiquidO detector - [200, 300] PE/MeV
- ★ Optimization of the technology on going!

LiquidO-Cube prototype

[J. Apilluelo et al/2026 //NST21 P01010](#)

3D-printed prototype

- ★ 3 cm size cube
- ★ 64 WLS fibres (Saint-Gobain BCF-91A), 3.2 mm pitch
- ★ Dual-end readout with SiPMs (Hamamatsu S13361-3050-AE-08)
- ★ Opaque scintillator: LAB + PPO + POPOP ~ 10 wt.% wax (scattering length ~ 0.5 mm) – not T dependent
- ★ Pixelated muon taggers - 64 pixels each, SiPMs read-out
- ★ PETsys TOFPET2 ASIC read-out
- ★ Coincidence trigger between muon taggers and cube

Goal: detection and reconstruction of cosmic-ray muon tracks.

LiquidO-Cube prototype

Opaque

Transparent

AntiMatter-OTech LiquidO detector

AntiMatter Tech

European
Innovation
Council

**UK
RI**

UK Research
and Innovation

10 ton LiquidO detector
Monitor nuclear reactors with neutrinos

Scalability demonstrator of the
LiquidO technology

<https://antimatter-otech.ijclab.in2p3.fr>

2028-...

Reactor Antineutrino Monitoring

- ★ IBD interaction: $\bar{\nu}_e + p \rightarrow e^+ + n$
- ★ **$\geq 10,000$ IBD $\bar{\nu}_e$ interactions per day** and 10 tons [$\geq 3\text{M}$ interactions/year]
- ★ LiquidO can improve $\geq 3\text{x}$ today's BG control (PID + vertex precision)
- ★ **S/BG > 100 expected with Reactor-ON** (unprecedented)
- ★ **S/BG > 1 with Reactor-OFF** (unprecedented)

Complementary information to current thermo-nuclear diagnosis

- Reactor state (on/off)
- Reactor power from neutrino rate
- Fissile content of core from rate and energy spectrum

Remote and non-intrusive

NEOS experiment talk @Neutrino 2022

Conclusions

- Liquid-based detector technologies play a central role in the present and future neutrino physics program
 - Different detection mechanisms lead to distinct trade-offs between detector mass, energy resolution, event imaging, and background rejection.
- **Water Cherenkov, liquid argon TPCs, and liquid scintillator detectors** provide complementary capabilities and together enable precision oscillation measurements, searches for CP violation, studies of astrophysical neutrinos, and rare-event searches.
- **Emerging concepts such as LiquidO** explore new optical regimes in scintillating media, recovering topological information at low energies and opening new opportunities for background rejection and event imaging.
- **The complementarity of liquid detector technologies is a strength of the field**

Back-up

DUNE X-Arapucas

X-ARAPUCA system based on SiPMs

- 1) PTP converts VUV light to a wavelength $<$ dichroic cutoff (128 nm \rightarrow 350 nm)
- 2) The dichroic filter allows the pass of the 350 nm photons.
- 3) Wavelength shifter bars (WSB) shift the light above the dichroic cutoff (350 nm \rightarrow 430 nm)
- 4) The light is trapped and after several reflections reaches the SiPMs

JUNO detector response

- **Energy non-linearity**
Scale uncertainty < 1%
Ensure the oscillation peak positions
- **Energy resolution**
 $\sigma_E < 3\%$ at 1 MeV
Resolve the fast component oscillation peaks

More info: Calibration Strategy of the JUNO experiment - [JHEP 03 \(2021\) 004](#)

JUNO Dual-Calorimetry

Objective: disentanglement of the degeneracy between the non-linearity and non-uniformity

	Fully correlated	Partially correlated	Non correlated
R^{LPMT}	R_{LSNL}^L	R_{NU}^L	$R_{NS}^L \cdot R_{QNL}^L$
↑	↑	↑	
Cancels	Cancels	Cancels	
↓	↓	↓	
R^{SPMT}	R_{LSNL}^S	R_{NU}^S	$R_{NS}^S \cdot R_{QNL}^S$

✓ Same energy deposition

✓ Common event vertex

✗ PMT-to-PMT difference needs proper treatment

Direct response comparison between LPMT calorimetry and SPMT calorimetry

LSNL = LS non-linearity, QNL = charge non-linearity
 NU = non-uniformity, NS = non-stability,

JUNO Dual-Calorimetry

20" LPMT

3" SPMT

$$\frac{R^{LPMT}}{R^{SPMT}} = \frac{R_{QNL}^L}{R_{QNL}^S}$$

Charge integration (QI)

FADC electronics

Photon-counting (PC)

95% of the charge detected in single PE regime for IBD events

Electronics could provide analog charge information (signal pulse amplitude and time over threshold)

Energy (PC) & Energy (QI) are complementary

SPMT charge detection is robust and redundant by design

Charge linear reference to the LPMT.

JUNO Calibration

- Achieving a light level of 1200 p.e. / MeV is not enough. Also have to keep the systematics under control

- Have an comprehensive calibration program consisting of 4 mutually complementary systems:
 - 1D: Automated Calibration Unit (ACU) deploys radioactive and laser (1ns, keV-TeV range) sources along the central axis
 - 2D: Cable Loop System (CLS) to scan vertical planes
 - 2D: Guide Tube to scan the outer surface of the central detector (where the CLS cannot reach)
 - 3D: Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV) operating inside the LS to scan the full volume
- + sPMT system

Goal is to keep the energy scale uncertainty $< 1\%$

Mini-LiquidO

LiquidO's timing Potential: Cherenkov vs Scintillation

Transparent media regime

- ★ Liquid scintillator: LAB alone (slow)
- ★ Water data allows confirmation of the Cherenkov peak time position
- ★ Remarkable separation using **only timing**
- ★ **Cherenkov light production threshold**

Mini-LiquidO

LiquidO's timing Potential: Optimised scintillator

(LAB + PPO) vs NW Opaque

- ★ Precise characterisation at the ns scale
- ★ Opacity negligible extra time-spread

Light Confinement Demonstration: Transparent vs Opaque

- ★ Water - Cherenkov-only
- ★ LAB - more light due to scintillation
- ★ LAB+PPO ($\leq 3\text{g/L}$) - amount of light increased
- ★ NW at 40°C - almost as transparent as usual LAB+PPO LS (less light due to 20% paraffine)
- ★ NW at 5°C - opaque

Faster collection and better light confinement in the opaque mode

Light Ball formation at ~4cm

Light confinement is observed
 → Major demonstration of the LiquidO technology

LiquidO-Cube

In the opaque case, fewer SiPMs have a signal during a muon event

Light confinement near the point of energy deposition

Enhanced tracking capabilities and position resolution!

	Transparent	Opaque
Position resolution	0.73 ± 0.03 mm	0.45 ± 0.02 mm

LiquidO Physics Potential

- ★ Powerful PID: topology of deposited energy
- ★ Energy Flow: time pattern
- ★ Tracking (mm)
- ★ Directionality
- ★ dE/dx (range)

Simulation